

Constraints to Effective Learners Disciplinary Management and Implementation Strategies by Principals in Public Secondary Schools in South Eastern Nigeria

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Abstract: *One of the leadership roles of the secondary school principal is learner discipline management. The ultimate aims and objectives make it clear that the goal of secondary education is to develop the individual's mental capacity and character for behaviour for higher education and useful living within the society since the future of any nation depends quite considerably on the quality of education it provides for its citizens. Falling standard of secondary education in Nigeria may not be unconnected with diminution to effective quality control. This underscores the purpose of this study to investigate the diminution to effective quality control of public secondary schools in South-Eastern states of Nigeria. In educational management and policy, there are two viewpoints on organizational control in secondary schools: one, which schools are highly decentralized organizations in which teachers have workplace autonomy and discretion; two, that schools are top-down bureaucracies in which teachers have little influence over school operations. These control measures if well implemented by school heads will enhance effective and efficient school administration.*

Keywords: *Indiscipline, Secondary education, Constraints to effective discipline, strategies of managing School discipline.*

I. Introduction

High School remains an introductory ground to emancipate and certify the requirement for human development. The teacher is faced with the challenges of educating, socializing, empowering and certifying students, but with the help of good teaching atmosphere (Nakpodia, 2013). The task of a teacher, which includes sustaining education system, does not rest on his or her professional competency alone, but on the entire features of the school climate (Ogbonnaya, 2014). For the efficient functioning of the school, school managements reserve power to control the conduct of students through reasonable rules and regulations. An effective school should ensure that learners are connected and supported by their educators and the principal who must practice good social, emotional skills and working collaboratively for effective instruction (Themane & Osher, 2014). The indiscipline problem in schools is ranked as a major problem among students of high schools in Nigeria. Students' misbehavior is a prevailing problem affecting schools not only in Nigeria but also across many countries around the globe.

Disciplinary problems dominate the issues of the day in both large and small schools both in towns and villages. Students disobey school rules and regulations with impunity. Disruptive behavior is a concern to schools and parents and to fellow students, whose education may be adversely affected. Learner discipline is defined as the absence of misbehaviour, and the students' responsibility to make the difference between right and wrong, and between socially acceptable and unacceptable behaviour (Belle, 2018). The absence of learner discipline is a very serious problem in secondary schools among adolescents (Edinyang, 2017). Nigeria is drastically worsening due to the inability of the school managers to effectively and efficiently manage learner discipline; the school must have the primary function of establishing a safe and non-disruptive environment that would facilitate effective teaching and learning (Ofojebe, 2007).

However, Belle (2018) found the following causes of a lack of learner discipline in secondary schools: the parenting styles of parents, working parents, ineffective parental discipline, the dysfunctional family, the learner's attitudes, the educator's attitudes, the principal's lack of authority and leadership in disciplining learners in schools and the peer group pressure among secondary school learners. Besides, On account of the seriousness of the problem of learner discipline, the Ministry of Education has spelled out the responsibilities of the principal in the Student Behaviour Policy document, which are as follows: "stimulate a school-wide approach in preventing indiscipline; lead by example by being regular and punctual; work in partnership with parents to develop and support the social and emotional skills of students; promote a positive school culture; acts promptly against all forms of student indiscipline; develop a sense of belonging to the school among the students; provide support to educators in their attempt to sustain high behaviour standards; arrange in-house sharing. The problem now is rather alarming and endangers the administration of the secondary school. It is against this background that the management of disciplinary problems in schools needs urgent attention. There is much work to be done since in some schools the situation has reached alarming proportions.

II. Objectives of the Study

This study titled "Constraints to effective learner disciplinary management and implementation strategies by principals in public secondary schools in south eastern Nigeria" aimed to review the hindrances to effective learners' disciplinary problems with regard to the types of disciplinary problems that are being experienced in secondary schools in south eastern Nigeria. The Constraints of disciplinary actions that are being experienced in these schools. The means of managing disciplinary problems in the said study area. Indiscipline in school is certainly a matter of immediate concern to the teaching profession. The study focused on the causes of the problems stated below are the main contributing factors that hinder effective management of disciplinary problems in the study area.

- i. Truancy is the disciplinary problem in secondary school.
- ii. Absenteeism is the disciplinary problem in the study area.
- iii. Fighting and stealing cause disciplinary problem in the study area.
- iv. Political, social and economic factors cause disciplinary problem in the said area.
- v. School curriculum and peer groups are the causes of disciplinary problem in the study area.
- vi. Family/Home is the cause of disciplinary problem in the study area.
- vii. School environment/teacher causes disciplinary problem in secondary school.

Finally, to recommend to stakeholders in education to address the indiscipline plight in south eastern Nigeria

III. Review of Related Literature

School discipline refers to regulation of children and the maintenance of orders (rules) in schools. These rules may, for example, define the expected standards of clothing, timekeeping, social behavior and work ethics (Nakpodia, 2013). The term 'discipline' may be applied to punishment which is the consequence of transgression of the code of behavior. For this reason, the usage of school discipline sometimes means the

administration of punishment, rather than behaving within the school rules. School discipline is an essential element in school administrations. This is because discipline is mode of life in accordance with laid down rules of the society to which all members must conform, and the violation of which are questioned and also disciplined (Zondi, 2015). The aim of school discipline is therefore to help the students to be well-adjusted, happy, achieve in academics and character and become useful to the society.

Basically, discipline problems in secondary schools occur when a student refuses to obey rules of the classroom or school. When rules that deal with human actions are eventually broken, they require some sort of penalty. In order to match the penalty with the rule violation, rules are presented in written format and punishment for violation is specified. The rules also relate to the stated function of education or the school process and, again common sense is prevailed in establishing disciplinary actions for breaking any rules. Discipline problems can be dealt with much more effectively if parents and school administrators could share the similar ideal version which leads to prolific missions. The researcher sees discipline as the training of mind and character aimed at producing self-control, ordered behavior and skillfulness.

Secondary Education

Many scholars defined secondary education in diverse perspectives. According to Row tree in Ogbonnaya (2014), secondary education refers to full time education provided in secondary schools for students between the ages of eleven or twelve and eighteen plus. Webster in Ogbonnaya (2014) defined it as ‘education in high school between the primary and the collegiate level’. It is defined by Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her National Policy on Education as the form of education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage. Ogbonnaya (2014) stated that secondary education is the form of education which children receive automatically after they have received primary school education. He maintained that secondary education constitutes post-primary education and sometimes serves as a link between primary education and university education. Secondary education in Nigeria is a six-year programmes, comprising of the junior secondary and senior secondary. Each level is of three years programme. The curriculum of the senior secondary schools is comprehensive and diversified in nature. The researcher defines secondary education as the education received by children of age eleven and eighteen after the successful completion of primary education.

Skinnerian Theory (1978)

The theoretical framework for this study was hinged on Skinnerian Theory and Bandera’s Social Learning Theory. The origin of environmental theories can be traced to a known psychologist named B.F. Skinners. B.F. Skinners’ operant conditioning hinges on the fact that learning best occurs when a reward is provided after an organism makes the desired response (operant). When a response occurs and is reinforced, the probability that it will occur again in the presence of similar stimuli is increased. Learning, therefore, occurs when behavioural change has occurred. In pursuing the experiment, Skinner developed units of learning called ‘contingencies of reinforcement’. The contingency of reinforcement is a sequence within which behavior (response) is followed by reinforcing stimuli. Skinner state the principle of learning that behaviours are naturally emitted without eliciting stimuli behavior (response) were called operant because their emission may be instrumental to reinforcing or punishing consequences. The operant is conditioned to occur more frequently, less frequently, or not at all depending upon whether it is reinforced, punished or ignored. Skinner performed his experiment in a controlled environment. A box that measure about 30.5cm on a side is programmed to present its inmate (rats and pigeons) with food as a reward for pressing a lever in a box. He discovered that once a particular type of consequence called reinforcement is well arranged, the behavior of the animal can be shaped at will. Skinner further posited that one of the most effective kinds of instruction might be done through the use of teaching machines. The author was referred to as the “father of the teaching machine”. The series are usually arranged in sequences of increasing complexity; when the pupils respond correctly, the machine has a way of rewarding them. The study is related to the theory because the theory talks about how hum an behavior is being conceived

from the process of interaction with the environment, the students in school when they interact with the facilities in the school, obey the rules and regulations stated by the school, there would not be need for indiscipline and it would aid to the achievement of school goals and objectives. The deficiency of the Skinnerian environment theory is that it fails to cover the personality traits of the individual. Thus, behavior is not learned through only environment but also by observation and imitation, and it's necessitated the introduction of social learning theory.

Social Learning Theory

The theory was propounded by Albert Bandura in 1977. The theory is based on the major premise that behavior is learned and can be unlearn. Behavior is, in general, a function of one's personality and the environment. Man is born with some innate potentials which the environment conditions. Similarly, one can influence his or her environment using personality qualities. Consequently, as one interacts in the environment, the adolescent consciously or unconsciously observes and imitates and displays behaviours of models. Hence, Bandura posits that there is interrelationship between man's personality, the behavior, and environmental factors.

Fig 1: Social learning theory: Albert Bandura

According to Bandura, the entire three elements: the person, the behavior and environmental situation are highly interrelated variables, each being capable of influencing the other. This can be illustrated using the diagram. The social learning theory emphasizes the importance of observing and imitating behavior, attitudes and emotional reactions of others. Thus, it focuses on learning by observation and imitation. Imitation and modeling of influential persons or models also depends on reinforcement. This reinforcement can either be direct or vicarious. In direct reinforcement, the person imitating the model received reinforcement directly. When a child, for instance, is praised for exhibiting a behavior, he has received direct reinforcement. In vicarious reinforcement, the person imitating the model does not get reinforced directly; it is rather the model that is reinforced. When one watch a model being reinforced, he is also reinforced indirectly. This is vicarious reinforcement. The motivation to identify with a particular model stems from the fact that this model possesses a quality which the individual taking an observed behavior, values, beliefs, and attitudes of the person with whom he is identifying. Relating it to the present study, individuals can model their behavior after parents, peers who have positive attitude and behavior towards education in order to enhance their academic standards. Therefore, this theory is relevant to this study in the sense that it will help students to learn the characteristics behaviours that make up their personality through observation and imitation. By so doing, they will desist from disruptive behavior that hinders teaching and learning in schools.

IV. Theoretical Studies

Some Forms of Disciplinary Problems Experienced in Secondary Schools

Truancy: This is irregular attendance to school or classes. Many factors are responsible for truancy among secondary school students. These factors include peer group influence, teacher methods of teaching and enforcement of discipline. Other reasons for truancy include poverty, especially where the child might engage in labour to raise money in order to fend for him/herself. Poor parenting/guarding methods among others may be responsible for truancy.

Absenteeism: Students' absence from school or class has become a recurring disciplinary problem in most day secondary schools. Secondary school rules and regulations are clearly violated when students do not attend to curricular and non-curricular activities organized by the school for their personal development. Wango (2015) asserts that absenteeism impacts negatively on teaching and learning. If a student has developed bad habit, he is also likely to consistently be absent from schools work.

Fighting: The key impetus for fighting during curricular and extra-curricular activities is the child's basic sense of inadequacy and feelings of not being valued or worthy (Basag, 2015). In other words, fighting results when the four psychological needs of the child have not been met. The need for love security, new experience and need for responsibility (Nakpodia, 2013). Fighting can cause minor or severe injuries, damage to human lives and properties leading to closing down of schools and many parents transforming their children to safer schools (Bowman, 2014).

Stealing: This is the removal of another person's property without his permission in many secondary schools, money and education materials such as books, laboratory and workshops equipment and tools owned by students or the school has been lost through stealing. Where the victims do not have alternative sources, teaching and learning is adversely affected. Substance Use" This is one of the most dangerous and most common school disciplinary problems (Buchart, 2018). It means taking drugs without prescription by the appropriate person. The drugs may include cigarettes and alcohol where hard drugs such as Indian hemp, cocaine and heroine are involved, a more severe disciplinary problem arises. The negative impact of substance abuse on child development cannot be overemphasized as it influences child's behavior.

Constraints to Effective Discipline in Secondary Schools

Research studies have identified many causes of disciplinary problems in secondary schools. Some of the constraints include parent/home influence, the role of the teacher, political, social and economic factors, learners with emotional problems arise, the kind of principal, the influence of gender public school versus private schools.

Parental/Home Influence: Alidzulum (2015) like most authors, regards parents as of the greatest importance in creating a conducive teaching and learning environment. It seems that the lack of parental involvement is the major constraint to disciplinary problems in secondary schools. Bowman (2014) is of the opinion that parents' failure to teach their children discipline is identified as the major contributing factor to disciplinary problems in secondary schools. Louw & Barnes (2013) also claimed that he has never seen a problem child, only problem parents. This means that those learners who behave badly at school do not receive proper discipline at home. In the researcher's opinion, the statement made by several authors indicate the extent to which parents are being blamed for the disciplinary problems in schools. Thus, bad behavior can be seen to have its roots in the quality of parenting as shown by erratic discipline, parental disharmony and approval of bad behavior.

Hayward (2015) further indicates that when parents show due civility and respect, their children reflect it in their interaction with their principals and teachers. On the other hand, if parents fail to exhibit reverence to others, the learners will imitate this behavior and show little or no respect for their educators. Some of the important factors related to the lack of parental involvement in school that influence discipline were identified by Short et al., (2014), namely single parent homes, lack of parental control at home, the negative influence of television, neighborhood and community problems that influence the home and values differences between the

home and the school. Teachers play a significant role in the management of school discipline. Bowman (2014) argued that teachers who do not actively involve learners in classroom activities may experience disciplinary problems. Research study also found that the involvement of learners in matters pertaining to their education reduces behavioural problems (Louw & Barnes, 2013). The writer's experience supports the above assertion that teachers who involve learners in class in matters pertaining to their education reduce behavioural problems (Louw & Barnes, 2013). There are emphasis that negative learner behaviour seems to decrease in schools where the teachers have created climates for learners' belongingness and involvement. Varham (2015) study found that learners have tendency of behaving badly at school because they feel that schooling is something that is done to them rather than a process in which they are valued as significant participants. In a study done by Mabela and Prinsloo (2018), it was indicated that learners prefer strict teachers who involve them in the management of discipline: teachers who are always ready to allow them to determine the consequences of their behavior. The researcher's experience show that some teachers are irresponsible and believe that their task is only to teach, and that the issue of discipline should be taken out of their hand by the system. That is why general concern is brought to the fore by several authors namely that teachers are no longer as committed to their professions as in the past. Many learners do not want to be forced to do something instead force encourages learners to act in stubborn manner. Teachers who do not prepare their lesson thoroughly or meaningfully promote negative self-esteem in learners who show little or no participation in classroom.

Political and Social Factors: Politically, Roussow (2017) indicate over emphasized placed on children's right one of the factors confusing principals, teachers and students in matters relating to the discipline of students at school. Some principals are under pressure to recognize learners' right and do not know to which point they should make allowance for their own voices. For instance, many newly appointed principals do report that the uncertain, confused and afraid of infringing upon students rights, and of being accused of misconduct. This mandate to protect learner's right, cause learners to behave beyond boundary. They try to influence bad behavior of their classmates negatively by exhibiting lack of discipline. Socially, children who experience social alienation from others often misbehave. According to Lewis (2016), this situation arises within most families where children feel rejected. This findings is supported by Butchart (2018) where he indicated that emotional disconnection from family, friends and peers result in feelings of isolation and alienation for the child, these feelings experienced by the child may ultimately developed into what is referred to as "psychological pains" which may ultimately cause gang violence, substance abuse, and many other discipline problems.

Emotional Problems of Learners: When learners have emotional problems, this may cause them to misbehave. They may behave badly in class because they need special attention, want to be leaders, want to be left alone, or want to hurt others as they have been hurt. Rossouw (2017) maintained that some learners play with cell phone in class, and when the teacher confront them, they start acting aggressively to impress their class mates.

Personality of the Principal: The kind of principal has attracted the attention of several researchers in respect of students' discipline at school. Short et al., (2014) advocates learners and educators participation in matters relating to the running of the school. Principal who are autocratic and self-centred end up with many disciplinary problems at school. In his findings, Alice came up with five types of principals namely A, B, C, D, and E. They have different attitudes towards discipline but they all believe that the attitude of the principal influences.

Principal A believes that when things go wrong and discipline is poor, he is the cause and that he is not a strong enough. Principal B does not accept the idea that teachers should take responsibility for any disciplinary problems. He believes that he himself has to deal with every situation at school concerning discipline in accordance with code of conduct. Principal C believes that he is influenced by the attitude of teachers although they sometimes put pressure on him, and that he may need the intervention of others. Principal D regards matters concerning discipline as a team effort. He also believes that his attitude plays a role but it has to be influenced by a collegial relationship with the staff. He sees himself as a teacher first, thereafter as a principal.

Principal E believes that discipline at school depends on the strictness of the principal. Alice (2010) believes that this kind of principal thinks the fundamental responsibility of the principal is to set the tone and discipline of the school. The type E principal also believes in leading by example – if he preaches punctuality, then he must also be punctual. The Curriculum: The relevancy of the curriculum to learners' need also influences discipline at school. Research found out that learners engage in several form of deviant behaviors if the curriculum is not able to offer them opportunities for self – development and a sense of personal worth, and do not address the aims that are promoted by society (Basag, 2014). Basag further maintained that learners resort to taking matters into their own hands if they believe that the curriculum is irrelevant and boring. According to Doveton (2013) indicates that deviant behavior is always experienced if the curriculum that is offered to learners is irrelevant to their interest and the needs of their community. Therefore, there is need for school administrators to emphasize the importance of linking the curriculum to the philosophy and customs of a particular society.

Strategies of Managing School Discipline

It has been observed by education stakeholders such as teachers and principal in Nigeria that education system at all levels is riddled with series of discipline problems. Unfortunately, when these problems go on unabated in secondary schools, the principals are blamed for non-performance of their duties and their failure to exhibit appropriate leadership behaviours to solve these perennial problems besieging education system. A significant challenge for principals today is to identify the situation of the school such as discipline problems, its effects on teaching and learning and strategies the principal should employ to mitigate them. Therefore, most principals set up some sort of rules and measures. It will be expected that positive results would be achieved whenever the rules are implemented and whereas if the rules are breached may create harmful repercussions. Keeping consideration the present scenario, the following considerations may be useful to principal: The authoritarian approach to discipline: In a research study conducted by Mtsweni (2014), the authoritarian style of leadership has been linked to autocratic communication, excessive control of learners, domination as well as compulsive exercise of power that may undermine the learners' feelings of freedom of security. The authoritarian approach to discipline suggests that administration of punishment cannot be rules out in the control of discipline of students. The right and authority of a principal is to inflict punishment on students for offences who breach school rules and regulation. It enhanced by the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) which specific people's right to personal liberty, and instances in which a person who has not attained the age of eighteen may be required of his right to liberty specifically, for educative and welfare purpose.

Suspension and expulsion of students: A student may be suspended or expelled where he infracts a grievous school rules. The student is probably given fair hearing prior to suspension and expulsion. It is recommended that parents are invited to the disciplinary committee hearing if the sanction of expulsion is contemplated. Parents have the right to appeal to higher person or body. It is principal's ability to inform the entire students the reason for the suspension or expulsion if it will have a deterrent effect on them. Without attempting an exhaustive list, the following may result to suspension or expulsion: truancy, tardiness, insubordination and disobedience to teachers, insulting a teacher, hitting a teacher, fighting with other students, leaving the school premises without permission, substance use, and refusal to stay for detention, lack of civility and destruction of school property. Punishment record must be kept by the school. Punishment record book is relevant information about students' punishment is entered by the head of this institution or any other teacher authorized by him. It contains information on date of the punishment, name of pupil, nature of the offence and person who administered the punishment. Exclusion: By exclusion, a student who infracts school rules may be asked to have limited contact with other people in the school. He may be permitted to enter the school premises solely to write an internal or external examination whole he remains barred from receiving lesson or participate in other activities.

Educative and Corrective Approach: In the guide for education on how to deal with discipline, the Department of Education (2015) advises educators to adopt alternative to corporal punishment for effective discipline such as:

Present possible alternative that focuses on rewarding learners for their effort, as well as for good behavior, discuss rules with learners and reach agreement on their right – learners will attempt to keep these rules because they have been consulted in their design, make use of measures that are respectful and dignified as well as physically and verbally non-violent use of disciplinary measures in such a way that the consequences of breaking rules are directly related to the learners who determine his/her readiness to gain self-control.

The bio-physical theory and alternative discipline: According to Head (2015), the biophysical theory explains human behavior by means of an analysis of metabolic, genetic and neurological factors. The theory indicates that lead poisoning, allergies and neurological impairment are the three widely biophysical causes of poor students' behavior. Honly (2015) further indicates that infection, a lack of sleep, a poor diet and vision problems are other bio-physical explanations for attention problem in children. Research shows that even when behavioural disorders are attributed to biological influences, the most effective treatment programmes are those that include both medical treatment and psychological intervention.

Psycho-dynamic theory and alternative discipline: For psychological health, child and young people must successfully complete a series of developmental stages, each which present accompanying psychological conflicts (Scheuermann & Hall, 2016). This means of any of the developmental stages are not satisfactorily completed or the conflicts are not adequately resolves, psychological difficulties and accompanying behavioural problems may result. Scheuerman & Hall (2016) demonstrated in the above model interventions which are more relevant to school settings. These include, among others, providing a warm, supportive climate where the principal and all the staff members are trained to interact in various appropriate therapeutic way with the learners. Such environments are designed to reduce unnecessary problems.

V. Empirical Studies

Studies on Discipline

The works of Kabuenui (2015) carried out a study on students' indiscipline, types, causes and possible solutions in the case of secondary schools in Cameroun. The study made use of descriptive research design and was guided by four research questions whereas two hypotheses were formulated and tested. The sample comprised of 3240 participants drawn from 120 schools (of the public, lay private and denomination) in four regions of Cameroun which were chosen by applying equal probability sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire composed of thirty (30) items. The study used triangulation sampling technique by applying probability sampling technique (simple random sampling) to arrive at the sampled students of the target population and other participants. Stratified sampling was equally used since the nature of the sample population is heterogeneous. Descriptive statistics parameter included percentage and mean which are used in answering the research questions while one way ANOVA was employed to test the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that the familiar and common type of indiscipline as disobedience to school teachers and prefect included collective misconduct of students and unacceptable habits. Students' indiscipline behavior was classified on three bases as follows: school based, society based and students based causes. Recommendations were made to include that the government of Cameroun, educationists, educators, policy makers, school administrators and parents should ensure that adequate facilities are provided in school for effective teaching and learning. This study is related to the present study since both discussed on students' indiscipline. The reviewed study was carried out in Cameroun while the present study was carried out in south Eastern States, Nigeria.

In a similar study, Sulaiman (2008) carried out a study on factors causing discipline problems in secondary school and teachers' strategies to overcome discipline problem among secondary schools in Kota Samarahan Division, Malaysia. It is also carried out at identifying the most common discipline problems and the most effective strategies used in overcoming discipline problems in secondary schools. The study used descriptive research design. The factors focused on personal, family, peers, teachers and school administration, school in general and Education Department. Five research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. The respondents were 300 teachers from seven schools in Kota Samarahan Division, Malaysia. The instrument employed was questionnaire. Data from the questionnaire were tabulated by using frequency counts and percentages and the findings were discussed descriptively. The results of the study indicated that some influencing factors that contributed to students' discipline problem were the lack of parental concern and love, lack of parental involvement in school activities, lack of support from parents, lack of motivation to study and parent-schools relationship. The findings revealed some strategies suggested and conducted by teachers had shown to be the best strategies to apply in order to curb discipline among secondary school students. This study is related to the present study as both discussed on discipline and reviewed study was carried out in Kota Samarahan Division; Malaysia but the present study was carried out in South Eastern States, Nigeria.

In the same vein, Ukang (2018) carried out a study on causes of indiscipline among students as viewed by primary school teachers in Nigeria. Indiscipline in Nigeria schools remained a source of great concern to stakeholders as it has caused a lot of mental, emotional and physical damages in the society. This research investigated the causes of indiscipline among students as viewed by primary school teachers in Nigeria. Furthermore, it also examines the influence of gender, school locale, years of teaching experience, and educational attainment on the respondent's views. This research employed a descriptive survey method involving 200 primary school teachers in Nigeria. They responded to a researcher designed questionnaire entitled "Causes of Indiscipline Questionnaire (CIQ)". In which the psychometric properties of the instrument were established. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The result revealed that the causes of indiscipline among students as viewed by primary school teachers in Nigeria were societal factors, government factor, parental factor, school factor and student factor respectively. In view of the findings, it is recommended that the government and school administrators formulate policies in schools to curb indiscipline among students. This study is related to the present study because both studies discussed discipline among students; also the reviewed study used descriptive survey as well as the present study. Both study used questionnaire for collection of data. However, there exist differences in the both studies. The reviewed study concentrated on primary school teachers and was carried out in Nigeria while the present study concentrated on secondary school students and was carried out in south Eastern states, Nigeria.

Studies on Moladjustice Behaviour

Aboh, Nwankwo & Agu (2014) carried out a study on factors influencing maladaptive behavior among High School students in Ishiagu Local Government Area of Ebonyi State. This study investigated factors influencing maladaptive behavior in which broken homes and negative attitudes of teachers serve as independent variables while maladaptive behavior serves as dependent variable. A total of one hundred (100) participants comprising 50 males and 50 females senior secondary (high) school adolescents' students between the ages of 12 – 16 and 17 – 21 and a mean age of 14 and 19 respectively were selected from the population of five secondary schools in Ishiagu, Ebonyi State, Southeast Nigeria, making use of randomized technique. They were administered with a 20 –item questionnaire in a dichotomous response style of yes/no. survey design was adopted and chi-square was applied in which results are obtained, revealed that broken homes significantly influenced maladaptive behavior with $\chi^2 (1, 1) = 21.16$ at $p < 0.01$ and also, negative attitude of teachers significantly influenced maladaptive behavior with $\chi^2 (1, 1) = 51.84$ at $P < 0.01$. The findings were discussed with respect to literature revealed and recommendations were made. The study is related to the present study because both studies discussed disciplinary behavior of students in schools; also the reviewed study used emperical as well as the

present study. However, there exist differences in the both studies. The reviewed study was carried out in Ishiagu Local Government Area of Ebonyi State which is part of South East States, Nigeria.

In the same vein, Muhammed, Phebe, Okaforcha & Muttawu (2019) carried out a study on effect of indiscipline on academic performance of students in Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi State. Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population of the study comprised 42 secondary schools in Dekina Local Government Area, with two thousand five hundred and three students (2,503) and three hundred teachers (300). A sample of two hundred and fifty respondents (250) which comprised two hundred and fifty teachers in Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi State formed the sample for this study. Respondents were randomly selected without replacement from six secondary schools. A 14 item questionnaire entitled “Effects of Indiscipline on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students Questionnaire (EIAPSSSQ) was used. The instrument for data collection was validated by three experts and the reliability estimate was 0.94. Two hundred and fifty questionnaires representing 100% came back qualified for processing and analysis. They were summarized to a four point response scale and benchmark of 2.50 and above was established as accepted. The research questions were answered descriptively using mean and standard deviation, while hypotheses were tested inferentially using t-test statistics. The result of the analysis showed that students and teachers agreed on the causes and effects of indiscipline in secondary schools. The result also showed that the two hypotheses were accepted. Based on the findings and conclusion the following recommendations were made: teachers and school administrators should be given proper training, government should monitor schools provide school amenities to schools and avoid policies that will push the students to a point of rebellion. Rules and regulation should be realistic and stated for the absorption of all students.

Summary of Reviewed Related Literature

The literature of this study focused on four main sub-headings: the conceptual framework, theoretical framework, theoretical studies and the empirical studies. Under the conceptual framework, concept such as discipline and secondary school education were reviewed. Discipline defines the limitations of an individual or a group of people. Under the theoretical framework, such theories as Skinnerian theory and social learning theory were reviewed. The theory gave an anchor that man is born with some innate potentials which the environment conditions. Similarly, one can influence his or her environment using the personality qualities. The study also discussed some related works under the theoretical studies in the area of forms of disciplinary problems encountered in schools, constraints to effective discipline and techniques of managing school discipline. Finally, empirical studies related to the study were reviewed. Although some empirical studies indicated constraints to effective discipline in secondary schools; a major problems that was evident from the literature was a general dearth of such research studies in Nigeria especially in the study area (South Eastern States). Most of the studies to the best knowledge of the researchers were conducted outside the country; therefore there is need to carry out this study in Eastern part of the country. It is the bid to fill this gap that motivated the study.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to review the Constraints to effective learner disciplinary management and implementation strategies by principals in public secondary schools in south eastern Nigeria. The broad goals of secondary education include to prepare individual for useful living within the society; and higher education. To achieve the objectives, there is need for effective management of disciplinary problems among secondary school students. It was discovered that students’ misbehaviour is a prevailing problem affecting schools not only in South Eastern States in Nigeria, but throughout the nation and the entire nations of the world. Students’ misconduct in the classroom interferes with teaching and learning and is thought to be forerunner to later school dropout and similar not in line with the norms and expectation of people living in the society. It is an anti- social behaviour that is not acceptable by society.

Recommendation

- i. School management should approach the problem of discipline with empathy for the possible problems the learners may be experiencing at home or at school that cause their poor behavior. This necessitates the services of a guidance and counselor in all schools.
- ii. Teachers and school administrators should be given proper training, government should monitor schools provide school amenities to schools and avoid policies that will push the students to a point of rebellion. Rules and regulation should be realistic and stated for the absorption of all students.
- iii. Parents should make education a priority for their children, this will make the children achieve better and behave in an acceptable manner.
- iv. The causes of disciplinary problems are addressed if teaching staff are actively involved in the teaching programmes of their school. This will lead to active participation of the students which subsequently confine their frivolities.
- v. Moderate right syndrome and formulation of behavioural expectations for teachers and learners will improve school discipline. In view of the above, a Code of Conduct for learners and staff is very important in all schools. It serves as an important stepping-stone towards fostering a culture of learning, mutual respect, accountability, tolerance, co-operation, personal development within the school and its surroundings.
- vi. Teachers and school administrators should be given proper training on how to manage the students and staff alike.
- vii. Government should monitor schools and ensure that teachers and students are fully involved or committed to teaching and learning and finally all the measures of curbing indiscipline as identified in this study should be taken seriously.

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